

Supporting Information

Toward a proximal cognitive model of co-morbidity:

Predicting individual differences in reading, spelling and maths in a sample of typically developing children (study 1)

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S1-S6 Tables

S1 Table. Predictors of reading fluency: original (MODEL 1) and alternatives.

Reading (fluency)	R^2 total Model	β	t	p	Unique	Common	Total	% R^2 Tot.	% R^2 Un.	Shared variance with:
ORIGINAL MODEL 1	0.487									
Orthographic Decision (OD)		0.36	5.39	< .0001	0.19	0.10	0.29	60	2	--
RAN		0.47	6.82	< .0001	0.12	0.05	0.17	34	39	--
Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching (V-Apwm)		0.20	2.87	< .01	0.03	0.16	0.20	40	7	--
MODEL 1 + Single Pseudo-word Repetition (SpwR)	0.488	0.04	0.55	0.58	0.00	0.08	0.08	16	0	
MODEL 1 + Phonemic Segmentation (PS)	0.497	-0.12	-1.57	0.12	0.01	0.10	0.11	23	2	OD and V-Apwm (11%)

Unique, common and total contributions for predictors of reading fluency in the original model (MODEL 1) and in the models obtained by adding phonological tests (Single Pseudo-word Repetition and Phonemic Segmentation tests, respectively). The column “Shared variance with” indicates the task(s) for which the shared variance of the model exceeded the 10% after a phonological test was added.

S2 Table. Original models (MODEL 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9) and addition of cognitive predictors.

Cognitive predictor added:	Original Model	% R^2 original Model	% R^2 with the added	Un.	Com.	Tot.	% R^2 Tot	% R^2 Un.	p	Shared variance with:
Raven	M. 1: Reading (fluency)	48.7	49	0.00	0.05	0.05	11	0		OD and RpwS (13%)
	M. 3: Reading (accuracy)	17.6	18	0.00	0.05	0.06	31	1		
	M. 5: Writing	29.2	29	0.00	0.05	0.06	19	1		
	M. 7: Calculation (speed)	37.9	41	0.03	-0.03	0.00	0	7	*	
	M. 9: Calculation (accuracy)	27.5	29	0.02	0.10	0.11	39	6		
Symbol Search	M. 1: Reading (fluency)	48.7	49	0.00	0.08	0.08	17	0		°
	M. 3: Reading (accuracy)	17.6	21	0.03	0.05	0.09	41	16		
	M. 5: Writing	29.2	31	0.01	-0.01	0.00	0	4		
	M. 7: Calculation (speed)	37.9	39	0.01	0.08	0.09	23	2		
	M. 9: Calculation (accuracy)	27.5	28	0.00	0.02	0.02	9	0		
Backward Span	M. 1: Reading (fluency)	48.7	49	0.00	0.08	0.08	17	0		
	M. 3: Reading (accuracy)	17.6	18	0.01	0.06	0.07	37	5		
	M. 5: Writing	29.2	30	0.01	0.00	0.00	1	2		
	M. 7: Calculation (speed)	37.9	38	0.00	0.07	0.07	18	0		
	M. 9: Calculation (accuracy)	27.5	30	0.02	-0.02	0.00	1	7		
Phonemic Fluency	M. 1: Reading (fluency)	48.7	49	0.00	0.06	0.06	13	0		*
	M. 3: Reading (accuracy)	17.6	23	0.05	-0.04	0.01	3	22		
	M. 5: Writing	29.2	30	0.01	0.01	0.02	6	2		
	M. 7: Calculation (speed)	37.9	38	0.00	0.03	0.03	9	0		
	M. 9: Calculation (accuracy)	27.5	28	0.00	0.02	0.03	9	1		

Unique, common, and total contributions (both as raw coefficient of Unique, common, and total contributions (both as raw coefficient of explained variance and as % of R^2 respect to the total variance explained by a model) after that each cognitive predictor is added to an original model. Additionally, in the p column, the significance of β of each predictor according regression analysis is reported. Table reported also information about the percentage of explained variance by the original model and of the model after that each cognitive predictor have been added. In the column “Shared variance with” were reported task(s) for which the shared variance with the added predictor exceed the 10%.

Note: * $p < .05$; ° $p < .01$.

S3 Table. Reading accuracy predicted by predictors of reading fluency (MODEL 1).

A. Reading (accuracy)	Coefficient		Percent	
Unique to Orthographic Decision (OD)	0.057		64.52	
Unique to RAN	0.000		.07	
Unique to Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching (V-Apwm)	0.007		7.37	
Common to OD and RAN	0.001		.63	
Common to V-Apwm and RAN	0.000		.09	
Common to OD and V-Apwm	0.025		27.84	
Common to OD and RAN and V-Apwm	-0.001		-.53	
Total	0.088			

B. Reading (accuracy)	β	t	p	Unique	Common	Total	% R^2
Orthographic Decision	.26	2.79	.006	.06	.02	.08	93
RAN	-.01	-.09	.930	.00	.00	.00	0
Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching	.09	.94	.347	.01	.02	.03	35

(A) Commonality coefficients and percentage of explained variance for the predictors of reading fluency (MODEL 1) used to predict reading accuracy. (B) Unique and common contributions of predictors in the model for Reading accuracy.

$R^2 = .088$; R^2 adjusted = .07; $F_{(3,128)} = 4.03$, $p < .01$

S4 Table. Predictors of reading accuracy: original (MODEL 3) and alternatives.

Reading (accuracy)	R^2	β	t	p	Unique	Common	Total	% R^2 Tot.	% R^2 Un.	Shared variance with:
	total Model									
ORIGINAL MODEL (3)	0.176									
Orthographic Decision (OD)		0.10	1.05	0.297	0.01	0.07	0.08	45	6	--
Visual-visual Pseudo-word Matching (V-VpwM)		0.25	2.87	< .01	0.05	0.04	0.09	51	28	--
Repetition of Pseudo-word Series (RpwS)		-0.24	-2.68	< .01	0.05	0.04	0.09	50	28	--
MODEL 3 + Single Pseudo-word Repetition (SpwR)	0.192	0.15	10.59	0.12	0.02	-0.02	0.00	1	9	
MODEL 3 + Phonemic Segmentation (PS)	0.18	-0.05	-0.47	0.64	0.03	0.07	0.09	51	14	RpwS (13%); OD and V-VpwM and RpwS (10%)

Unique, common and total contributions for predictors of reading accuracy in the original Model (MODEL 3) and in the models obtained by adding phonological tests (Single Pseudo-word Repetition and Phonemic Segmentation tests, respectively). The column “Shared variance with” indicates the task(s) for which the shared variance with Pseudo-words repetition and Phonemic segmentation exceed the 10%.

S5 Table. Another original model for Reading accuracy (MODEL 5) and alternatives.

Reading (accuracy)	R^2					Unique	Common	Total	% R^2 Tot.	% R^2 Un.	Shared variance with:
	total Model	β	t	p	1						
ORIGINAL MODEL (5)	0.292										
Orthographic Decision (OD)		0.38	4.62	< .0001	0.12	0.08	0.20	70	41	--	
Single Pseudo-word Repetition (SpwR)		0.27	3.17	< .01	0.06	-0.06	0.00	0	21	--	
Repetition of Pseudo-word Series (RpwS)		-0.32	-3.49	< .001	0.07	0.05	0.12	42	24	--	
MODEL 5 + Visual-visual Pseudo-word Matching (V-VpwM)	0.29	0.04	0.51	0.61	0.03	0.03	11	1	0		
MODEL 5 + Visual-auditory Pseudo-word Matching (V-ApwM)	0.30	-0.07	-0.79	0.43	0.00	0.01	2	1	0		
MODEL 5 + Auditory-auditory Pseudo-word Matching (A-ApwM)	0.29	-0.01	-0.11	0.91	0.01	0.01	2	0	0		
MODEL 5 + Phonemic Segmentation (PS)	0.29	0.04	0.41	0.68	0.00	0.01	0.01	4	0		

Unique, common and total contributions for predictors of reading accuracy in the original Model (MODEL 5) and in the models obtained by adding the visual-visual, visual-auditory and auditory-auditory versions of the pseudo-word matching tasks, and the phonemic segmentation task to the original Model 6. The column “Shared variance with” indicates the task(s) for which the shared variance with the added predictors exceed the 10%.

S6 Table. Predictors of calculation: original models (MODEL 7 and 9) and alternatives.

	A: Calculation (speed)								B: Calculation (accuracy)							
	R^2 total Model	Un.	Com.	Total	% R^2 Total	% R^2 Unique	p	Shared variance with:	R^2 total Model	Un.	Com.	Total	% R^2 Total	% R^2 Unique	p	Shared variance with:
ORIGINAL MODEL (7/9)	0.379								0.275							
Number Order (NO)		0	0.08	0.08	21	0	°	--		0.03	0.11	0.14	50	11	°	--
Arithmetic Facts (AF)		0.19	0.14	0.32	86	50	*	--		0.04	0.11	0.15	55	14	*	--
Computation Strategies (CS)		0.05	0.13	0.17	46	13	*	--		0.06	0.12	0.18	65	21	*	--
MODEL 7/9 + Computation Procedures (CP)	0.38	0.00	0.03	0.03	9	0	--	--	0.28	0.00	0.02	0.02	7	0	--	--
MODEL 7/9 + Backward Counting (BC)	0.38	0.01	0.00	0.00	0	1	--	--	0.28	0.00	0.01	0.01	4	0	--	--
MODEL 7/9 + Arabic Number Reading (ANR)	0.38	0.01	0.08	0.09	23	1	--	--	0.29	0.01	0.07	0.08	29	4	--	--
MODEL 7/9 + Arabic Number Spelling (ANS)	0.38	0.00	0.00	0.00	1	0	--	--	0.28	0.00	0.01	0.02	5	1	--	--

Unique, common, and total contributions of predictors of calculation in the original Models (MODEL 7 and 9) and in the models obtained by adding the Computation Procedures, Backward Counting, Arabic Number Reading, and Arabic Number Spelling tests were added to the original models. The column “Shared variance with” ” indicates the task(s) for which the shared variance with the added predictors exceed the 10%.